

STUDY OF THE CRYSTALS OF *p*-NITROANILINE AND *p*-NITROTOLUENE BY THE X-RAY SINGLE CRYSTAL ROTATION METHOD.

BY MATA PRASAD AND R. N. MERCHANT.

From the rotation photographs taken about the three crystallographic axes of single crystals of the two substances, the following dimensions of the unit cell were determined: *p*-Nitroaniline (15.31Å, 6.085Å, 8.36Å; $\beta = 126^\circ 11'$), *p*-nitrotoluene (6.41Å, 14.10Å, 15.39Å). A large number of planes were identified on oscillation photographs and the halvings showed that the first crystal belongs to the space group C_2^1 , and the second to C_2^1 .

Complete structure analyses of various aromatic compounds, e.g., naphthalene and anthracene (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1930, 4, 557; *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, A140, 79), diphenyl (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1932, 7, 43; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 167; *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, A142, 333; *Nature*, 1933, 131, 153), durene (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, A141, 594; 1933, 142, 659) etc. show that the size and shape of the constituent benzene rings remain unaltered in all these compounds. This rigidity of the benzene ring is a very useful guide in the determination of the structure of any new substance. James, King and Horrocks (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1936, A153, 225), have found, however, that the benzene ring in *p*-dinitrobenzene is slightly puckered, that carbon atoms to which the nitro groups are attached being situated about 0.1Å above or below the plane containing the other four nuclear carbon atoms. It is with an idea to find out whether the ring in similar simple benzene derivatives is plane or puckered that a study of these compounds has been started in this laboratory. The present paper gives the results of a preliminary investigation to determine the space group to which the crystals of *p*-nitroaniline and *p*-nitrotoluene belong.

p-Nitroaniline.

The crystals of *p*-nitroaniline belong to the monoclinic prismatic class and develop the following faces :

$$r\{20\bar{1}\}, \quad p\{110\}, \quad q\{011\}, \quad c\{001\}.$$

The axial ratio is $a : b : c = 2.5198 : 1 : 1.4215$, $\beta = 126^\circ 11'$. (Groth, "Chemische Krystallographie," V, p. 181).

p-Nitroaniline was purified by repeated crystallisations from chloroform. Thin plates, bright yellow in colour, were obtained by a slow evaporation of the solution of the substance in chloroform. The melting point was found to be 147° .

Rotation photographs taken about the three crystallographic axes, using X-rays from a Shearer gas-tube fitted with copper target ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$), give the following dimensions of the unit cell.

$$a = 15.31 \text{ \AA}, \quad b = 6.085 \text{ \AA}, \quad c = 8.63 \text{ \AA}, \quad \beta = 126^\circ 11'.$$

The axial ratio is $a : b : c = 2.516 : 1 : 1.419$ which agrees well with that given in Groth (*loc. cit.*).

Oscillation photographs were taken at suitable small angles about the *a*, *b* and *c*-axis and the planes corresponding to the spots identified with the help of Bernal's chart. The following tables (I and II) give the list of planes together with an approximate idea of their intensities for which the usual symbols have been used.

TABLE I.

Axial planes.		Prism planes (okl).		Prism planes (hcl).		Prism planes (hko).		
001	w. m.	011	w. m.	201	v. w.	$\bar{2}01$	m. s.	
002	m. s.	012	m.	202	v. w.	$\bar{2}02$	w.	
020	w.	022	w. m.	203	v. w.	—	130	w.
200	m.	031	v. w.	401	w.	$\bar{4}01$	w. m.	
600	w.					$\bar{4}02$	m.	
						$\bar{4}03$	w.	
						404	w. m.	
						601	w. m.	
						620	v. w.	
						603	w.	
						802	w.	

TABLE II.

General planes.

111 m.s.	$\bar{1}11$ m.	411 w.	$4\bar{1}1$ v.w.
112 w.m.	$\bar{1}12$ w.	412 m _a	$4\bar{1}2$ m.
113 w.m.	...	413 w.m.	$4\bar{1}3$ w.
121 w.m.	$\bar{1}21$ w.	...	$4\bar{1}4$ v.w.
122 w.	$\bar{1}22$ w.	422 v.w.	$4\bar{2}2$ v.w.
123 w.	...	423 w.	...
131 v.w.	131 w.	432 v.w.	...
132 v.w.	$\bar{1}32$ v.w.	511 w.	$\bar{5}11$ w.
211 m.s.	$\bar{2}11$ m.s.	512 w.	$\bar{5}12$ w.m.
212 v.w.	$\bar{2}12$ v.w.	513 w.m.	$\bar{5}13$ w.
213 w.m.	213 w.	...	$\bar{5}14$ w.
...	214 v.w.	...	$\bar{5}22$ v.w.
...	$\bar{2}21$ w.	523 w.	$\bar{5}23$ w.
222 v.w.	$\bar{2}22$ v.w.	611 w.	611 w.
231 v.w.	$\bar{2}31$ v.w.	...	$\bar{6}12$ w.
311 v.w.	$\bar{3}11$ v.w.	...	$\bar{6}14$ v.w.
312 v.w.	$\bar{3}12$ v.w.	621 v _a w _a	$\bar{6}21$ w.
313 m.	313 w	622 w _a	622 w.
321 v.w.	$\bar{3}21$ w.	623 w.	$\bar{6}23$ w.
322 v.w.	$\bar{3}22$ v. w.	...	$\bar{7}11$ v.w.
323 w.	323 w.	...	$\bar{7}12$ w.m.
			$\bar{7}13$ v.w.
			714 w.m.

The above tables shows that (h0l) planes are halved when h is odd. Also (010) planes are halved. These halvings assign the crystal to the space group C_{2h}^2 with Γ_m Bravais lattice. The number of molecules required by the space group is four. Since the number of molecules (mol. wt. 138.06) calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell and the specific gravity of the crystals (found to be 1.428) is also four (accurately 4.05), one *p*-nitroaniline molecule as a whole forms an asymmetric unit of the cell.

p-Nitrotoluene.

The crystals of *p*-nitrotoluene belong to the orthorhombic bipyramidal class and develop *b* (010), *c* (001), *o* (211), *p* (110) and *q* (011) faces. The axial ratio is

$$a : b : c = 0.9111 : 1 : 1.0971 \text{ (Groth, } loc. cit., p. 362).$$

These crystals have been studied by Sreenivasaiah (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1927, 2, 151) by the Powder and Laue methods. He obtained the following values for the dimensions of the unit cell

$$a = 10.17 \text{ \AA}, \quad b = 11.18 \text{ \AA}, \quad c = 12.3 \text{ \AA}$$

and assigned the space group Q_2^1 to the crystal.

Pure substance crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether gave suitable single crystals for the present work. The substance vapourises very rapidly when exposed to the atmosphere, a crystal weighing about 1 mg. disappearing in nearly one hour. For this reason comparatively large crystals had to be used and shorter exposures were given.

The dimensions of the unit cell were calculated from the rotation photographs about the three principal axes and were found to be $a = 6.41 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 14.10 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 15.39 \text{ \AA}$ (Plates IV, V, VI)

The axial ratio is $a : b : c = 0.4545 : 1 : 1.091$ which agrees with that given in Groth except that $a : b$ is halved.

Oscillation photographs were taken about the three crystallographic axes and the planes given in Tables III and IV identified.

TABLE III.

Axial planes.	Prism planes (okl).	Prism planes (hcl)	Prism planes (hko).
002 v.s.	012 w.	205 w.m.	120 s
004 m.s.	014 w.	206 w.m.	130 m.s.
006 w.	016 w.	207 w.m.	140 s.
008 v.w.	018 } or } w.	208 w.	150 w.m.
020 m.s.	028 }	201 m.	160 w.
040 v. s.	022 w.	202 w.	170 w.m.
050 w.m.	024 m.s.	203 w.m.	210 m.s.
060 w.m.	026 w.	204 w.	220 v.w.
080 w.	032 w.m.	206 m.	230 w.
200 s.	034 w.	207 w.m.	240 w.m.
	036 w.	208 w.	260 w.
	042 m.s.	301 w.	310 w.m.
	044 m.		330 w.
	046 v.w.		340 w.
	052 v.w.		
	054 w.		
	056 v.w.		
	062 v.w.		
	064 m.		

TABLE IV.

General planes.

111 s.	153 v.w.	235 w.m.
112 v.s.	154 v.w.	236 w.
114 w.m.	155 w.	241 w.m.
115 m.	156 v.w.	242 w.
116 w.	161 w.	243 m.
117 w.m.	163 w.	245 v.w.
118 w.	164 v.w.	251 v.w.
121 m.s.	165 v.w.	253 v.w.
122 m.s.	171 w.m.	256 v.w.
123 m.s.	172 w.m.	261 w.
124 m.s.	173 w.	262 w.
125 w.m.	211 m.	263 v.w.
126 m.	213 w.m.	271 } or } w.
127 m.s.	214 w.m.	272 }
128 v.w.	215 w.m.	311 w.m.
131 s.	216 m.	312 v.w.
132 s.	217 w.	313 v.w.
134 w.m.	218 w.	314 w.
135 w.	221 w.m.	321 } or } m.
136 w.m.	222 w.	322 w.
137 v.w.	223 w.	323 w.
141 m.s.	224 } or } w.m.	325 w.
142 m.	214 }	331 w.m.
143 m.	225 w.	332 v.w.
144 v.w.	226 w.	333 v.w.
146 w.m.	227 w.	341 } or } v.w.
151 w.m.	231 w.	342 }
152 w.	234 w.	

It will be seen from the above tables that (okl) planes are halved when l is odd. The crystals of *p*-nitrotoluene, therefore, belong to the space group Q_2^5 which requires eight asymmetric units to complete the symmetry of the unit cell. The number of molecules calculated from the dimensions of the cell and the specific gravity of the crystals is also eight (accurately 7.98). The molecules in the cell are, therefore, asymmetric.

Sreenivasaiah's results calculated from the above expression are in close agreement with those obtained by us. The space group assigned by Sreenivasaiah (*loc. cit.*) is, however, not supported by the results of our investigation.

PRASAD & MERCHANT

Rotation photographs of p-nitroaniline.

Plate I.
a-axis

Plate II.
b-axis

Plate III.
c-axis

PRASAD & MERCHANT

Rotation photographs of p-nitrotoluene.

Plate IV.
a-axis

Plate V.
b-axis

Plate VI.
c-axis

